

SURVEY ON EDUCATION OF GIRLS AND WOMEN – OPPORTUNITIES AND OBSTACLES*Mrs. Neelam Gupta**Ms. Pallvi Priya**MES's Pillai College of Education Research, Chembur***ABSTRACT**

The paper provides an overview of the state of education with respect to women and highlights some of the issue of women's access to education in India. Today the education of women has become one of the most important concerns of 21st century. We observe in our day to day life as to how women are victimized by various social evils. Women empowerment is the vital instrument to expand women's ability to have resources and to make strategic life choices. This is possible only with the help of education. Education of women is essential for the upliftment of economic, social and political status of women. It is the process of guarding them against all forms of violence. The study reveals that women are relatively disempowered and are hardly aware of their educational rights. It is found that acceptance of unequal gender norms by women are still prevailing in the society.

INTRODUCTION

Ban Ki Moon, Secretary General of United Nations quoted that- “There is no more valuable investment than in a girl's education.”

The term ‘Women Education’ refers to every form of education that aims at improving the knowledge, and skill of girls and women. It includes general education at schools and colleges, vocational and technical education, professional education, health education, etc. Girl's education is about so much more than knowledge. By ensuring that a girl has equal access to education, employment and adequate health care, the benefits will be passed on to her children (both boys and girls), community and her country.

In recent times the number of girls going to the school is more than in the past few decades. However, despite progress, women and girls continue to face multiple barriers based on gender and equal enjoyment of the right to quality education. Primary education is now a fundamental right. When a girl or a woman is ensured of her rights, the society at large is ensured of its sustainability. Women have been sharing half the sky, so they cannot be neglected in having their active participation for the development of one's country. There have been a number of initiatives adopted by the Government of India such as - ‘Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao’ and ‘Sarvasiksha Abhiyaan’ to enhance the literacy rate of females in India. The study aims at evaluating the economic condition and education level of women.

OBJECTIVE

- (1) To highlight various policies and programs held by government.
- (2) To discuss, opportunities and challenges in the way of girls education.
- (3) To suggest some points for improvement in girls education.

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

In many countries, it is clear that a girl child faces discrimination throughout her childhood and adulthood. They are often considered ‘temporary property’ as they have to move to their spouse's house post marriage. Of the 1.3 billion people in poverty 70% are women. Women earn the 3/4th the income that men earn in non-agricultural sector. Women are known to occupy only 10% of parliamentary seats and 6% of the Cabinet positions in the world. According to 2011 census data, female literacy rate stands at 53.67% where male literacy rate was 75.26%. There are currently 31 million girls of primary school age that are not in school. 1 in 9 girls in the developing world are married before the age of 15. There are 774 million illiterate people in the world and two-thirds are female.

Government Schemes have proven to be helpful in reducing female foeticide and infanticide rates, by providing that a girl child is not a burden on her parents. Moreover, these schemes also ensure that girl children are more independent once they reach adulthood. Apart from government schemes, there are other schemes launched private banks to benefit to the girl child.

1. Sukanya Samridhi Yojana	4. Mazi Kanya Bhagyashree Scheme
2. Balika Samridhi Yojana	5. Nanda Devi Kanya Yojana
3. Mukhyamantri Rajshri Yojana	6. Mukhyamantri Kanya Suraksha Yojana

Some of the schemes announced by the government are listed below :-

METHODOLOGY

A valid questionnaire was made to examine the minds of the youth and some parents, regarding education to girls and women. The study was carried out amongst the youth and parents. We got data from 70 people including both male and female.

Following were the questions asked in the survey :-

1. Are you aware of the several Rights to Education?
2. What are the opportunities for women in education?
3. Amongst the male and female, who has better ability to develop our society?
4. Would you allow the girls or women in your house, to move out of town, for pursuing higher education or their desired career?

If NO, then why?

RESULT

Are you aware of right to education	94% yes	6% No	0% don't know
Do you know the schemes and plans that are run by Government of India for education of girls and women?	50% yes	10% No	40% few of them
Would you allow the girls or women in your house, to move out of town, for pursuing higher education or their desired career? If No, then why?	70% because they want	20% because she wants	10% No because of economical problem and unsafe environment
Education is an opportunity for girls.	90% agreed	7% don't know	3% No
Who have more abilities to develop their family and society	85% Educated women	0% Uneducated women	15% Both
According to you by what percentage has the girls enrolment increased in higher education?	26% below average	24% above average	60% average

In females, by what percentage has the dropout case increased?	10% Inadequate facilities in schools and College	70% Economical issues	20% Marriage or other responsibilities
Do the girls and boys, in your family given same opportunity for education ?	88% Yes	12% No	0%
Would you allow the girls in your house to pursue a career in mechanical engineering /technician/pilot/loco pilot ?	88% yes	4% No	8% it doesn't suit for girls.

SUGGESTIONS

Despite of the several schemes and plans , there is a big gap in literacy rate amongst the men and women. There are several obstacles which still prevail in our society. There is a need for change in the mindset of people. The approach and conduct of our society also needs amendment, with respect to the progress of women in education and career. Some strategies that we can be implemented are as follows :

- Every parent should know the benefits of education and they should enrol their female child in schools and colleges.
- Government should check whether or not, all the schemes and plans ,reached to the everyone. Teachers should make people aware of each and every scheme.
- Female teachers are recruited in large numbers, especially in rural areas .They should be a role model for girls, in terms of education.
- Facilities like drinking water, toilets, sanitation and safety should be increased in schools and colleges.
- Opening girls schools in large number in rural areas.
- Child marriage should be stopped. Also, the responsibilities that keep them from getting education at higher level, should be reduced.
- Parents should encourage and support their girls to pursue their dreams.

CONCLUSION

As Gandhi ji said , “ If you educate a man you educate an individual but if you educate a woman, you educate an entire family.” In India, today Government of India is trying to decrease gaps in literacy rate. However, despite of those efforts, there are many things that are still need to done .Many area of country are still behind in providing adequate education to the girls. The Central and state governments must act together to make education available for them .Parents and teachers must also contribute to eradicate gender bias.

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